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Factors affecting employees' job satisfaction at Vinh Long radio and television station

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Abstract

The study's objective is to determine factors impacting employees' job satisfaction at Vinh Long Radio and Television (TV) Station. The authors used convenient sampling to collect data from 233 employees working at Vinh Long Radio and TV Station. The exploratory factor analysis and multivariable linear regression help the study find seven factors affecting job satisfaction. They include nature of work, training and promotion, income, leadership, colleagues, working environment, work pressure, and work autonomy. In which, work pressure has the most negative influence on job satisfaction of employees working at Vinh Long Radio and TV Station.

Keywords: Satisfaction; Job; Employee; Radio and TV station

1. Introduction

In the economic integration context of the globe, a lean and productive human resource is one of the core competitive advantages of an enterprise. The competition of human resource attraction is always a problem for enterprises. Business owners focus on both the recruitment process and remuneration policies to improve employee satisfaction and retention. Currently, many Vietnamese companies are facing the "brain drain" which leads them to difficult situations. The fact shows that despite huge investments in human resources, businesses are still struggling to find the satisfying answer to this problem.

In Vietnam, there are five types of paid TV services: cable TV, terrestrial digital TV, digital satellite TV, mobile TV, and Internet broadcasting. Vietnam has a total of 10 million cable TV subscribers, 200,000 terrestrial TV subscribers, 1 million digital satellite TV subscribers, 1 million Internet TV subscribers, and 480,000 mobile TV subscribers. These numbers tell a fierce competition of the television industry on multi-technology platforms. To improve competitiveness, it requires radio and TV stations to build strategies to retain and develop high-quality human resources, especially technology personnel. If radio and TV companies have good remuneration policies, flexible working hours, friendly working culture, and suitable conditions to develop, employees will be more excited at work. If employees have high satisfaction, radio and TV companies can attract and retain talented people. From the above reality, the study "Factors affecting employees' job satisfaction at Vinh Long Radio and TV Station" is carried out.

2. Theoretical framework and research hypotheses

2.1. Theoretical framework

Job satisfaction is a positive response to work (Quinn and Staines, 1979). It reflects the employee's level of satisfaction at work, that is, the employee's feelings or emotions for work (Kreitner and Kinicki, 2007). Job satisfaction is the degree

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to which employees love their jobs, which is an attitude based on their perception (positive or negative) about their job or working environment (Ellickson and Logsdon, 2002). According to Kusku (2003), job satisfaction shows the extent to which workers’ needs and desires are met.

2.2. Research hypotheses

Based on a literature review, it has shown that the factors of work nature, training and promotion, income, and benefits have a positive influence on job satisfaction (Spector, 1985; Luddy, 2005; Tatsuse and Sekine, 2010; Dung, 2005; Loc et al., 2015; Diem, 2018; Giao and Nha, 2020; Tai, 2021). Besides, the factors of welfare, managers, and colleagues also have a positive influence on job satisfaction (Dung, 2005; Ly, 2011; Loc et al., 2015; Giao and Nha, 2020; Tai, 2021). Moreover, Spector (1985) and Luddy (2005) have indicated that supervisors’ support and work autonomy have a positive effect on job satisfaction.

The study uses the group discussion method (qualitative research) with experts, administrators, and staff working at Vinh Long Radio and TV Station. The results of the group discussion have set out research hypotheses and appropriate scales for the model. The study proposes eight hypotheses. H1: The nature of work has a positive influence on job satisfaction. H2: Training and promotion have a positive effect on job satisfaction. H3: Income has a positive impact on job satisfaction. H4: Leadership is positively correlated with job satisfaction. H5: Colleagues positively influence job satisfaction. H6: Working conditions positively affect job satisfaction. H7: Welfare has a positive influence on job satisfaction. H8: Work autonomy positively impacts job satisfaction. The research model is as below.

Figure 1 Proposed research model

Table 1 Interpretation of observed variables in the research model

Sign	Description	Scale
Nature of work		
NW1	The job is suitable for me.	Likert 1-5
NW2	The job allows me to show my skills.	Likert 1-5
NW3	I understand my job well.	Likert 1-5
NW4	The work I am in charge of is important to the organization’s operation.	Likert 1-5
NW5	My performance is properly evaluated and recognized	Likert 1-5
Training and promotion		
TP1	Vinh Long Radio and TV Station organizes appropriate training activities for my work.	Likert 1-5
TP2	Vinh Long Radio and TV Station offers their employees the necessary skills to meet job requirements	Likert 1-5

TP3	Vinh Long Radio and TV Station offers opportunities for me to learn and improve my job skills.	Likert 1-5
TP4	Vinh Long Radio and TV Station offers a clear promotion roadmap.	Likert 1-5
TP5	Vinh Long Radio and TV Station offers fair training policies for all employees.	Likert 1-5
Income		
IN1	The income matches my workload.	Likert 1-5
IN2	The salary and bonus structure is fair and reasonable.	Likert 1-5
IN3	I am well aware of my income policy.	Likert 1-5
IN4	My income can cover my daily expenses.	Likert 1-5
IN5	The income is higher than other companies.	Likert 1-5
Leader		
LE1	I get the support of the leader.	Likert 1-5
LE2	Leaders have high qualifications.	Likert 1-5
LE3	The leader supports me at work.	Likert 1-5
LE4	Leaders treat employees fairly.	Likert 1-5
LE5	The leader offers me good conditions to improve my ability and skills.	Likert 1-5
LE6	The leader guides me at work.	Likert 1-5
Colleagues		
C01	Colleagues are ready to help me at work.	Likert 1-5
C02	Colleagues are friendly and sociable.	Likert 1-5
C03	Colleagues motivate me to work.	Likert 1-5
C04	My colleagues are reliable.	Likert 1-5
Working condition		
WO1	Clean and comfortable working environment.	Likert 1-5
WO2	I feel safe at work.	Likert 1-5
WO3	My work pressure is not high.	Likert 1-5
WO4	Overtime at work is not regular.	Likert 1-5
WO5	I am not worried about losing my job.	Likert 1-5
Benefit and welfare		
BW1	Vinh Long Radio and TV Station has a full range of insurance policies for employees.	Likert 1-5
BW2	Vinh Long Radio and TV Station has good benefits (sick leave, family business, retirement, maternity leave).	Likert 1-5
BW3	Vinh Long Radio and TV Station regularly organizes holidays for employees.	Likert 1-5
BW4	Vinh Long Radio and TV Station's welfare policies are fair and public.	Likert 1-5
Work autonomy		
WA1	I have the right to make decisions within my scope of work.	Likert 1-5
WA2	I can contribute to new working methods.	Likert 1-5
WA3	I have the freedom at work.	Likert 1-5
WA4	I can change the way I work for better results.	Likert 1-5
Job satisfaction		
JS1	I want to commit to Vinh Long Radio and TV Station in the long term.	Likert 1-5
JS2	I love my job at Vinh Long Radio and TV Station.	Likert 1-5
JS3	I am proud to work at Vinh Long Radio and TV Station.	Likert 1-5

3. Research methodology

3.1. Analytical method

The quantification of factors affecting employees' job satisfaction working at Vinh Long Radio and TV Station is conducted in three steps. Step 1: Using Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient to test the correlation among observed variables. Step 2: Using the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) method to test the convergent and discriminant level of the observed variables. Step 3: Using multivariable linear regression to test the research hypotheses.

3.2. Data collection method

The study applied convenience sampling to survey 233 employees working at Vinh Long Radio and TV Station. According to Hair et al. (1998), in exploratory factor analysis (EFA), the observation/measurement variable proportion should be 5:1, meaning that 1 measure requires at least 5 observations. As presented by Tabachnick and Fidell (1996), the suitable sample size for the regression analysis is determined as $N \geq 50 + 5 * m$ (m is the number of independent variables). Therefore, the research sample size meets the requirements of reliability for the hypothesis test.

4. Research results and discussion

4.1. Test the reliability of scales

Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is used to eliminate "garbage" variables, which means variables with item-total correlation values less than 0.3 are excluded (Nunnally, 1978; Peterson, 1994; Slater, 1995). The satisfying scales have Cronbach's Alpha values greater than 0.6 (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Table 2 shows that the scales have high reliability (the lowest reaches 0.698) and the item-total correlation value of each observed variable is satisfactory (the lowest is 0.392). Therefore, all variables are counted in the exploratory factor analysis (EFA).

Table 2 Scale reliability test result

Factor	Number of observed variables	Min corrected item-total correlation	Cronbach's Alpha
Nature of work	5	0.507	0.828
Training and promotion	5	0.701	0.912
Income	5	0.477	0.867
Leader	6	0.687	0.919
Colleagues	4	0.613	0.887
Working condition	5	0.392	0.752
Benefit and welfare	4	0.467	0.698
Work autonomy	4	0.699	0.886
Job satisfaction	3	0.719	0.850

Source: Survey value, 2021

4.2. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Based on the result of EFA for independent variables in the research model, indicators are as follows. The significance level (Sig.) is less than 0.05, KMO = 0.855 (in the range from 0 to 1), factor loading coefficients of all observed variables are greater than 0.5 (except for the WN5 receiving this value lower than 0.5, so it is excluded). The total variance explained value after removing BC5 reaches 74.064% > 50%. This suggests that the study data are consistent (Gerbing and Anderson, 1988). The analysis results from nine factors: F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, F6, F7, F8, and F9. The observed variables have different convergent and discriminant levels compared with the proposed model, so there are changes in factors' names. The calibration result gives nine factors: leadership, opportunity and promotion, income, colleagues, work autonomy, nature of work, benefits, work pressure, and working environment. The two new factors (work pressure and working environment) are separated from the working "condition factor" of the proposed model. Similarly, the EFA for

the dependent variable gives satisfactory values. The significance level (Sig.) is less than 0.05, KMO = 0.728 (in the range from 0 to 1), factor loading values are all greater than 0.5. The total variance extracted reaches 78.967% > 50%. This proves that the study data are consistent (Gerbing and Anderson, 1988). Thus, the analysis creates one factor, F10 - satisfaction. All factors are summarized in the table below.

Table 3 Factors created from the exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

Sign	Observed variables	Factor
F1	6 variables: LE1, LE2, LE3, LE4, LE5, LE6	Leader
F2	5 variables: TP1, TP2, TP3, TP4, TP5	Training and promotion
F3	5 variables: IN1, IN2, IN3, IN4, IN5	Income
F4	4 variables: CO1, CO2, CO3, CO4	Colleagues
F5	4 variables: WA1, WA2, WA3, WA4	Work autonomy
F6	4 variables: NW1, NW2, NW3, NW4	Nature of work
F7	4 variables: BE1, BE2, BE3, BE4	Benefit
F8	3 variables: WP1, WP2, WP3	Work pressure
F9	2 variables: WO1, WO2	Working condition
F10	3 variables: JS1, JS2, JS3	Job satisfaction

Source: Survey data, 2021

4.3. Multivariate linear regression

Following the exploratory factor analysis (EFA), multivariable linear regression helps determine factors affecting employees' job satisfaction at Vinh Long Radio and TV Station. The results are in table 4.

Table 4 Multivariate linear regression analytical result

Factor	Standardized coefficient	Significance level (Sig.)	Variance Inflation Factor VIF	Hypothesis
Leader	0.341	0.000	1.750	H1: accepted
Training and promotion	0.277	0.000	1.390	H2: accepted
Income	0.399	0.000	1.457	H3: accepted
Colleagues	0.111	0.003	1.603	H4: accepted
Work autonomy	0.086	0.000	1.116	H5: accepted
Nature of work	0.101	0.000	1.333	H6: accepted
Benefit	-0.029	0.354	1.632	H7: rejected
Work pressure	-0.443	0.000	1.262	H8: accepted
Working environment	0.078	0.022	1.290	H9: accepted
Adjusted R ² = 0.795; Durbin-Watson stat = 2.323; Significance (Sig.F) = 0.000				

Source: Survey data, 2021

Table 4 shows that the adjusted R² coefficient reaches 79.5%, proving that job satisfaction is highly explained by factors in the model. The Sig.F value of the model is much smaller than $\alpha = 5\%$, so the regression model is significant. Durbin-Watson = 2.323 and VIF < 2 which means that the model does not have autocorrelation and multicollinearity. The test

results show that independent variables are statistically significant except the "benefit" variable. The factors of leadership, training and promotion, income, colleagues, work autonomy, nature of work, and working environment are positively correlated with employees' job satisfaction. Meanwhile, the factor of work pressure is negatively correlated with job satisfaction. In other words, if employees highly appreciate the leadership, training and promotion, income, colleagues, work autonomy, nature of work, and working environment, their job satisfaction will be higher. Besides, the higher the work pressure, the lower the job satisfaction. The factor of work pressure has the strongest impact on job satisfaction of employees working at Vinh Long Radio and TV Station.

5. Conclusion

The study applied quantitative methods to determine factors affecting job satisfaction at Vinh Long Radio and TV Station. Research results have demonstrated positive factors for employee job satisfaction, including leadership, training and promotion, income, colleagues, work autonomy, nature of work, and work environment. Meanwhile, the factor of work pressure negatively affects the job satisfaction of employees. Among the affecting factors, work pressure has the most influence on job satisfaction. From the above results, some managerial implications are proposed. Firstly, building a team and assigning work in teams so that members can share work, thereby reducing work pressure. Secondly, improving the salary and bonus security system, building a public and clear job evaluation roadmap. Thirdly, operating seminars or meetings to strengthen the connection between managers and employees. Leaders should exchange experiences and working skills with their staff. Fourthly, opening training courses according to the needs of employees. Fifthly, applying apprenticeships and flexible job rotation within the same department to create more job opportunities.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no competing or potential conflicts of interest.

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